

ELECTROSPUN CELLULOSE ULTRA-FINE FIBERS FROM KRAFT PULP

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SUMMARY

In this study, we aim to produce regenerated cellulose fibers of high strength and dimensional stability by electrospinning. We demonstrate, for the first time, that kraft pulp/NMMO solutions could be electrospun into micro- and nano-fibers. SEM, IR, TGA and tensile tests are used to establish the fiber structure-property relationships.

Keywords: Kraft Pulp, Electrospinning, Regenerated Cellulose, Ultra-fine Fibers

INTRODUCTION

Kraft pulp, a type of cellulose, is a product of the most dominant pulping technique that accounts for two-third of the pulp productions in North America. Cellulosic fibers are hydrophilic, and thus highly susceptible to loss of mechanical properties upon moisture absorption. Furthermore, commercial pulp fibers are seldom straight and continuous, and contain many deformations along their length. They do not allow the fibers' strength potential to be fully realized. Kraft pulp fibers, which have an average diameter 30 μ m, have a tensile strength of 700 MPa and elastic modulus of 20 GPa. In comparison, cellulose nanofibrils, which have an average diameter of 5nm, have a tensile strength of 10 GPa and elastic modulus of 150 GPa [1]. Strength evidence shown in cellulose nanofibrils suggests that smaller fiber diameter would lead to a lower probability of including defects and a smaller flaw sizes in the fiber, thereby increasing the mechanical properties. It has been shown that regenerated cellulose fibers ranging from 90nm to 10 μ m in diameter could be fabricated by electrospinning using cotton linter, spruce cellulose and α -cellulose [2,3,4]. It follows that high-strength cellulose micro- and nano-fibers could be produced from electrospinning due to the small diameter of the electrospun fibers. In this study, it has been demonstrated, for the first time, that electrospun cellulose micro- and nano-fibers could be produced from kraft pulp. Regenerated cellulose fibers by electrospinning using kraft pulp can potentially result in the development of more high value-added products, including structural and packaging materials, for the pulp and paper industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Kraft pulp (DP~1200) is added into 50% water solution of NMMO. Anti-oxidant propyl gallate (~1wt% of kraft pulp) is added to prevent oxidation. Water is removed from the solution to achieve 85wt% NMMO and 15wt% water with RotoVap (Buchi) at 80°C. Upon complete dissolution, a clear brown solution was obtained. 1, 2 and 3wt% of kraft pulp solutions in NMMO/water are electrospun in this study. The solution is placed in a 20 ml syringe wrapped with a heating jacket at 90°C. The flow rate is 1-3mL/hour. The ambient temperature is 100-140°C. The tip-target distance is 5cm. The accelerating voltage is 5-10kV. The coagulant is water at 20°C. The electrospun fibers are washed in water at 20°C for 12 hours and air-dried at 20°C for 12 hours. Characterization techniques used include SEM, ATR spectroscopy, TGA, and tensile testing.

Figure 1. The electrospinning setup to produce electrospun fibers from kraft pulp solutions

Taguchi's Experimental Design

To systematically examine the effects of the process parameters on the electrospun cellulose fiber formation and diameter, an experimental design is required. Four process parameters, including polymer solution concentration, nozzle temperature, voltage and solution flow rate, were found to have an effect on the electrospinning process. Table 1 is a summary of the process parameters (factors) and the three levels to be used in the design of experiments.

Table 1. 3-level-4-factor Experimental Design

Factors	Levels		
	-1	0	+1
Concentration (wt%)	1	2	3
Temperature (°C)	100	120	140
Voltage (kV)	5	7.5	10
Flow Rate (mL/hr)	1	2	3

To investigate the effects of the four factors on fiber formation and diameter, a full factorial experimental design would require a total of $3^4 = 81$ experiments. To reduce the number of experiments and maintain the effectiveness of the experimental design, Taguchi's experimental design is set up as shown in Table 2 [5].

Preliminary trials showed that 1wt% kraft pulp solution consistently led to film formation instead of fiber formation (refer to SEM of 1wt% samples). Consequently, the experimental design in Table 2 was modified and expanded from 9 to 18 experiments, as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Taguchi's experimental design for electrospun cellulose fibers from kraft pulp

Experiment	Conc (wt%)	Temperature (C)	Voltage (kV)	Flow Rate (mL/hr)
1	1	100	5	1
2	1	120	7.5	2
3	1	140	10	3
4	2	100	7.5	3
5	2	120	10	1
6	2	140	5	2
7	3	100	10	2
8	3	120	5	3
9	3	140	7.5	1

Table 3. Modified Taguchi's experimental design for electrospun fibers from kraft pulp

Experiment	Conc (wt%)	Temperature (C)	Voltage (kV)	Flow Rate (mL/hr)
1	2	100	5	1
2	2	120	7.5	2
3	2	140	10	3
4	2	100	7.5	3
5	2	120	10	1
6	2	140	5	2
7	2	100	10	2
8	2	120	5	3
9	2	140	7.5	1
10	3	100	5	1
11	3	120	7.5	2
12	3	140	10	3
13	3	100	7.5	3
14	3	120	10	1
15	3	140	5	2
16	3	100	10	2
17	3	120	5	3
18	3	140	7.5	1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fiber Formation

A summary of the conditions for electrospun cellulose fiber formation is shown in Table 4. All but 3 sets of experimental conditions were fiber-forming. The 3 sets of non-fiber-forming conditions at 3wt% polymer solution concentration share a common factor of 5kV voltage. It can thus be concluded that 5kV is too low a voltage to produce electrospun cellulose fibers from a 3wt% kraft pulp solution for all other experimental conditions.

Table 4. Conditions for electrospun cellulose fiber formation

Exp	Conc (wt%)	Temp (C)	Voltage (kV)	Flow Rate (mL/hr)	Fiber formation
1	2	100	5	1	yes
2	2	120	7.5	2	yes
3	2	140	10	3	yes
4	2	100	7.5	3	yes
5	2	120	10	1	yes
6	2	140	5	2	yes
7	2	100	10	2	yes
8	2	120	5	3	yes
9	2	140	7.5	1	yes
10	3	100	5	1	no
11	3	120	7.5	2	yes
12	3	140	10	3	yes
13	3	100	7.5	3	yes
14	3	120	10	1	yes
15	3	140	5	2	no
16	3	100	10	2	yes
17	3	120	5	3	no
18	3	140	7.5	1	yes

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Electrospun cellulose fibers from 1wt% kraft pulp solution

Figure 2 shows the SEM of samples from preliminary trials (using various electrospinning conditions) collected both from water surface in the form of film and as single fibers, which would fuse together to form a film. This observation could be due to the presence of solvent in the fibers coagulated in water bath that causes the fibers in contact with each other to fuse together and form a film. The 99wt% of solvent in the polymer solution appears to be too high for effective solvent removal in the water bath to allow fibers to remain separated after water coagulation.

Figure 2. On the left, sample collected from water surface. On the right, samples collected as single fibers and the fiber bundle fused to form a layer of film

Electrospun cellulose fibers from 2wt% kraft pulp solution

Figure 3 shows the electrospun fibers from 2wt% kraft pulp solutions. The SEM image shows that submicro- and micro-fibers can be electrospun from the 2wt% kraft pulp solutions. Electrospun micro-fibers with 25.2 μ m in average fiber diameter were collected in the single fiber form. Smaller fibers, including those on the submicron scale, were collected in the form of random fiber bundles.

Electrospun cellulose fibers from 3wt% kraft pulp solution

Figure 4 shows the electrospun fibers from 3wt% kraft pulp solutions. At 5kV, no fibers could be produced. Visual observations suggest that the electrospun fibers from 3wt% solutions are larger in diameter than the 2wt% solutions.

EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(μ m)	EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(μ m)	EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(μ m)
#1 100°C 5kV 1mL/hr		AVE: 25.2 STDEV: 11.9 MIN: 4.5 MAX: 56.9	#4 100°C 7.5kV 3mL/hr		AVE: 1.3 STDEV: 0.7 MIN: 0.3 MAX: 3.3	#7 100°C 10kV 2mL/hr		AVE: 1.1 STDEV: 0.5 MIN: 0.4 MAX: 2.6
#2 120°C 7.5kV 2mL/hr		AVE: 0.9 STDEV: 0.4 MIN: 0.4 MAX: 1.8	#5 120°C 10kV 1mL/hr		AVE: 2.1 STDEV: 0.9 MIN: 1.0 MAX: 4.6	#8 120°C 5kV 3mL/hr		AVE: 13.5 STDEV: 6.9 MIN: 9.6 MAX: 22.2
#3 140°C 10kV 3mL/hr		AVE: 2.8 STDEV: 1.4 MIN: 0.7 MAX: 5.9	#6 140°C 5kV 2mL/hr		AVE: 7.6 STDEV: 3.7 MIN: 2.0 MAX: 21.0	#9 140°C 7.5kV 1mL/hr		AVE: 1.1 STDEV: 0.4 MIN: 0.6 MAX: 2.1

Figure 3. Electrospun fibers from 2wt% kraft pulp solutions (scale bar: 100 μ m)

EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(um)	EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(um)	EXP	SEM (500X)	DIA(um)
#10 100 C 5kV 1mL/hr	No fiber		#13 100 C 7.5kV 3mL/hr		AVE: 7.8 STDEV: 3.9 MIN: 2.2 MAX: 17.2			
#11 120 C 7.5kV 2mL/hr		AVE: 2.0 STDEV: 1.9 MIN: 0.5 MAX: 8.7	#17 120 C 5kV 3mL/hr	No fiber				
#12 140 C 10kV 3mL/hr		AVE: 3.2 STDEV: 3.0 MIN: 0.7 MAX: 16.0						

Figure 4. Electrospun fibers from 3wt% kraft pulp solutions (scale bar: 100µm)

Average Fiber Diameter Measurements

Table 5. Electrospun Cellulose Fiber Diameters

Exp	Conc (wt%)	Temp (C)	Voltage (kV)	Flow Rate (mL/hr)	Fiber Diameter (µm)	Standard Dev (µm)	%Standard Dev (µm)
1	2	100	5	1	25.2	11.9	47%
2	2	120	7.5	2	0.9	0.4	48%
3	2	140	10	3	2.8	1.4	49%
4	2	100	7.5	3	1.3	0.7	54%
5	2	120	10	1	2.1	0.9	46%
6	2	140	5	2	7.6	3.7	49%
7	2	100	10	2	1.1	0.5	51%
8	2	120	5	3	13.5	6.9	51%
9	2	140	7.5	1	1.1	0.4	32%
10	3	100	5	1	n/a	n/a	n/a
11	3	120	7.5	2	5.9	4.6	77%
12	3	140	10	3	4.7	3.1	66%
13	3	100	7.5	3	1.6	0.9	57%
14	3	120	10	1	2.0	1.9	93%
15	3	140	5	2	n/a	n/a	n/a
16	3	100	10	2	7.8	4.0	51%
17	3	120	5	3	n/a	n/a	n/a
18	3	140	7.5	1	3.2	3.0	92%

Electrospun cellulose fibers from 2wt% kraft pulp solution

For the 2wt% fibers, the average fiber diameter ranges from 0.9 to 25.2 μm . This shows that submicron and micro-fibers could be produced using the electrospinning process by varying the process parameters. The %standard deviation of the 2wt% average fiber diameter has an average of 48%, which is significantly lower compared to that of the 3wt% fibers at 73%. It can therefore be concluded that 2wt% is the optimum concentration to produce cellulose fibers via electrospinning.

Electrospun cellulose fibers from 3wt% kraft pulp solution

For the 3wt% fibers, the average fiber diameter ranges from 1.6 to 7.8 μm . As discussed above, the average fiber diameter from 3wt% kraft pulp solution has a significantly higher %standard deviation. This could be attributed to the higher viscosity of the 3wt% solution that causes the difficulty in forming a stable electrospinning jet.

Response Surface Analysis

Using DesignExpert, the effects of voltage and temperature on the average fiber diameter are examined. Figure 5(a) shows that an increase in the voltage and temperature would reduce the average fiber diameter. Based on Figure 5(a), the electrospun fibers from 2wt% solutions always have an average diameter of less than 19.2 μm . Figure 5(b) shows that an increase in the temperature would reduce the average fiber diameter. However, the effect of flow rate on the average fiber diameter does not have a definitive trend. At 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the fiber diameter decreases when flow rate increases from 1 to 2 mL/hr, and the fiber diameter then increases when the flow rate increases from 2 to 3 mL/hr. The effect of flow rate on the average fiber diameter appears to be relatively small compared to the other factors including concentration, temperature and voltage.

Figure 5. (a) Voltage and Temperature Effects on Fiber Diameter; (b) Flow Rate and Temperature Effects on Fiber Diameter

Attenuated Total Reflectance Spectroscopy

The 1450 cm^{-1} band which is characteristic for asymmetric bending in CH_3 in lignin confirmed the presence of lignin in both the electrospun and natural fibers. The band at

1160 cm^{-1} could be ascribed to the asymmetric bridge C-O-C stretching in cellulose and hemicellulose. The 898 cm^{-1} band is characteristic for the asymmetric out-of-phase ring stretching in cellulose. The band at 1045-1055 cm^{-1} corresponds to the native xylan spectra. The lignocellulosic chemical structure was preserved during the electrospinning process as shown in the ATR spectra. [6]

Figure 6. ATR Spectra of Electrospun versus Raw Pulp Fibers

Thermogravimetric Analysis

From Figure 7, the 50% thermal degradation temperatures for raw pulp and electrospun fibers are 307°C and 315°C, respectively. This suggests that the electrospun fibers have a higher thermal stability. This behavior could be related to the crystallinity degree as well as the molecular chain orientation of the fibers, as an increase in either property is associated with increases in the thermal stability [7].

Figure 7. %Mass Loss versus Temperature for Electrospun and Kraft Pulp Fibers

Tensile Testing

Mechanical properties of the single fiber samples from Experiment #1 (2wt%, 100°C, 5kV, 1mL/hr) were tested using KES-G1 microtensile tester. Ten samples of 2cm in gauge length were tested at a deformation rate of 0.01cm/s. As shown in Figure 8, the fiber diameters of the ten samples vary significantly, ranging from 7μm to 52μm. This could be due to different degrees of stretching and elongation of the electrospinning jet in the instability zone of the electrospinning process, which results in varying diameter along the same fiber. The fiber diameter is shown to have an effect on the mechanical properties as depicted in Figure 9. The elastic moduli and breaking strengths of the ten single fiber samples increase with decreasing fiber diameter. This is because a smaller fiber diameter would result in a lower probability of including defects and smaller flaw sizes in the fiber. Increases in mechanical properties with decreasing fiber diameter could also suggest that fibers with smaller diameter have a higher crystallinity and/or molecular chain orientation because of more stretching and elongation experienced during the electrospinning process.

Figure 8. (a) Stress-strain curves of electrospun cellulose single fibers; (b) Enlarged section of the curves. The value next to each curve is the single fiber diameter.

Figure 9. (a) Fiber diameter effect on Elastic Modulus and (b) Breaking Strength

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated, for the first time, that electrospinning is a feasible process to produce submicron and micron-sized regenerated cellulosic fibers from kraft pulp. Taguchi's Experimental Design is used to conduct a systematic study of the effects of polymer concentration, nozzle temperature, voltage, and flow rate on the fiber diameter. Lower concentration, higher nozzle temperature and higher voltage would result in smaller fiber diameter. Flow rate does not appear to have a definitive effect on the fiber diameter. 2wt% kraft pulp solutions are shown to be the optimum concentration for electrospinning because 1wt% solutions would produce cellulose film and 3wt% solutions would produce fibers with a larger diameter variation than 2wt% solutions. IR spectra show that the raw pulp and electrospun fibers have similar chemical structures. TGA data shows that the electrospun fibers are more thermally stable than the raw pulp fibers. Tensile testing shows that elastic modulus and breaking strength increase with decreasing fiber diameter, indicating that the smaller fibers have fewer defects, higher crystallinity and/or molecular chain orientation.

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